

The Persistence of Hesitancy in Accepting COVID-19 Vaccine: A Study on the Inhabitants of Rural Manipur, India

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Abstract

While it has been more than a year since India first began its COVID-19 vaccination campaign, hesitancy toward the vaccine continues to pose a significant challenge in achieving herd immunity. This paper examines the factors for the persisting existence of COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy among the rural inhabitants of Manipur and how the discipline of medical anthropology can assist in mitigating this challenge. Since it was a qualitative study, 100 non-vaccinated individuals of 18 years and above were telephonically interviewed. The result shows complacency, rumours, conspiracy theories, misinformation, fake news, inaccessibility or unavailability, the time factor, distrust toward government and health care workers, and anti-vaccine propaganda, which were thought to have been debunked, continue to fuel the persistence of vaccine hesitancy. Furthermore, the efforts of the government and its agencies to discredit inaccurate information about the vaccine have been largely unsuccessful. As a result, people are less informed about the correct details of the vaccine. Medical anthropology, with its rich methodological and theoretical approach and comprehension levels, can be a valuable tool in addressing the issue of vaccine hesitancy.

Key Words: COVID-19; Vaccination; Vaccine Hesitancy; Rural Inhabitants; Medical Anthropology; Anthropology of Medicine.

INTRODUCTION

Medical anthropology is a specialised branch that integrates social, cultural, and biological insights to examine the multifaceted factors influencing health and well-being, the experience and distribution of illness, the prevention and treatment of sickness, healing processes, and the cultural significance of diverse medical systems. In essence, medical anthropology focuses on understanding the many factors contributing to disease or illness and how different populations respond to these health challenges. Various anthropologists define it as a discipline that elucidates the mechanisms influencing individuals and groups' responses to illness and disease, emphasising behavioural patterns. It also encompasses the biocultural aspects of human behaviour, considering biological and sociocultural factors and historical and contemporary interactions in influencing health and disease. Ultimately, medical anthropology explores human health and disease, health care systems, and how communities adapt and respond to disease and

illness, employing anthropological and social science theories and methods to examine health, illness, and healing questions (McElroy, 1996; Baer *et al.*, 1997; Hasan, 1959; Fabrega, 1972; Bhasin, 2027).

The diverse application of anthropological knowledge spans various fields, demonstrating its potential to enhance human conditions significantly. Through extensive anthropological research, valuable insights have been gained into the complexities of human societies and cultures. Armed with this theoretical knowledge, applied anthropologists have effectively utilised their expertise to address practical needs as they arise. Using anthropological principles and methodologies to real-world situations, they have made valuable contributions to numerous domains, such as public health, development, education, business, and social policy.

One notable area where medical anthropologists have significantly impacted is public health. Their understanding of cultural beliefs, practices, and social structures has proven crucial in designing and implementing successful health interventions. For instance, anthropologists have played vital roles in combating infectious diseases by considering local customs and traditions when developing vaccination campaigns or disease prevention strategies (Farmer, 2003). Recognising the cultural significance of health-seeking behaviours has effectively improved healthcare access and delivery in diverse communities (Kleinman and Benson, 2006; Hahn and Inhorn, 2008).

One key aspect that medical anthropology can bring to the table is the recognition of the diversity of perspectives within different communities. And in this case, vaccine hesitancy is not a monolithic phenomenon, and its drivers can vary widely based on cultural, socioeconomic, and historical contexts. Acknowledging and respecting this diversity is crucial for tailoring effective interventions that respect local beliefs and values.

COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy has emerged as a significant obstacle in achieving widespread vaccination coverage and controlling the spread of the virus. Understanding the factors contributing to vaccine hesitancy is crucial for designing effective communication strategies and interventions that resonate with diverse communities. Medical anthropology offers a unique lens through which researchers can examine the cultural beliefs, social dynamics, and historical influences that shape individuals' attitudes toward COVID-19 vaccines. However, despite the wealth of theoretical applications of medical anthropology, its potential in addressing vaccine hesitancy has been relatively underexplored. Against this backdrop, the present study attempts to uncover the reasons behind COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy and suggest valuable anthropological measures to alleviate this problem.

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COVID-19, also known as SARS CoV2, spread quickly around the globe after its first case was discovered in China in December 2019. As a result, the outbreak was declared a Public Health Emergency of International Concern in January 2020 and a pandemic in March 2020. Since then, the Indian Government has taken aggressive measures to combat the pandemic and initiated the health system's preparedness to respond to all aspects of COVID-19 management. As a result, India maintained one of the greatest recovery rates internationally and the lowest positive and death rates during the pandemic. Furthermore, on 16th January 2021, India began its COVID-19 vaccination program across the country, which witnessed the vaccination of the highest number of beneficiaries covered anywhere in the world on the first day (MoHFW, 2021). Since then, the Government of India and the state of Manipur, in particular, have been doing everything they can to ensure that every citizen gets their COVID jab. When writing this paper (October 2023), India crossed 2 billion vaccine doses just a year after its launch, the world's largest vaccination drive against Coronavirus (ibid). In celebration of this milestone achievement, Prime Minister Sri Narendra Modi, on 17th July 2022, tweeted, "India creates history again! Congrats to all Indians on crossing the special figure of 200 crore vaccine doses. Proud of those who contributed to making India's vaccination drive unparalleled in scale and speed. This has strengthened the global fight against COVID-19."

Despite this monumental achievement, new COVID-19 cases continue to haunt people across the country. Many people are still dying each day due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the only means to protect people is through mass vaccination to develop herd immunity. However, some sections of people, especially in rural areas, continue to resist vaccine doses, putting individuals' well-being and the whole country's health at risk. According to WHO, vaccine hesitancy is one of the greatest challenges to global health (Griffith *et al.*, 2021; Dhama *et al.*, 2021). Is the government not performing enough to convince the people, or is the problem in the individual's observations, experience, judgement, knowledge, values, and beliefs?

Based on the author's observation spanning over one and a half years, it is evident that the government has been taking extensive measures to overcome barriers to vaccination within the population. These efforts include making vaccine doses readily available at no cost to individuals. This proactive approach by the government demonstrates its commitment to ensuring widespread vaccine access. In addition to providing free vaccines, the government has shown great dedication to reaching remote tribal areas despite the challenges posed by rugged terrains and long distances. Health officials and workers have travelled hundreds of kilometres to administer vaccines in these hard-to-reach areas. This demonstrates their commitment to

leaving no one behind and ensuring that even the most marginalised communities have access to vaccination (Shaiza, 2021; Zimik, 2021; Ranjan, 2021).

There are three vaccines available in India. The Oxford-Astra Zeneca vaccine is locally referred to as Covishield, Bharat Biotech-ICMR indigenous vaccine named Covaxin, and the Russian Sputnik V vaccine, which is imported (Kumar *et al.*, 2021). Vaccine hesitation during the initial phase of the vaccination process is expected and understandable due to misinformation, distrust in the government, belief in conspiracy theories, false rumours, fake news circulating on WhatsApp and Facebook, and the voice of anti-vaccine propaganda on the internet. However, it has been more than a year since the vaccination began. So why does vaccine hesitancy continue to persist when all the false myths, rumours, fake news, and mistrust are thought to be busted due to the government's relentless effort? For instance, a fake viral WhatsApp message claimed that French virologist and Nobel Prize winner Luc Montagnier predicted that "all vaccinated people will die within two years" and that the COVID-19 vaccination drive was a "big blunder" was one of the biggest obstacles to the vaccination drive (Roy, 2021). Regrettably, many individuals, particularly those residing in the Ukhrul district of Manipur, were initially influenced by such predictions during the early stages of the vaccination campaign. However, it has been established that this message, along with other misinformation pertaining to the vaccines, has since been refuted. Despite these efforts, a large portion of the population remains hesitant about receiving the COVID-19 vaccination.

In the Ukhrul district, according to the latest (of 05th October 2022) available information, only 42.68% (47,697) and 34.87% (38,965) of 18 years and above have received first and second COVID-19 doses, respectively (NHMM, 2022), out of the total population of over one lakh thirty thousand. These figures indicate an extremely poor response to the vaccination campaign by the people of the Ukhrul district. Therefore, it demands an investigation to determine why people are still reluctant to receive the COVID-19 vaccine.

One must also keep in mind that vaccine decision-making is complex, context-specific, and varies across time, place, and vaccines. It is also influenced by individual observations, experiences, knowledge, and even values and beliefs (Kashyap, 2021). According to Tarfe, vaccination hesitancy is always complex and stems from various structural and historical variables. Due to a history of scepticism in the health system and a lack of health information, poor and marginalised people have resisted previous vaccination campaigns in India, such as measles and rubella (Tarfe, 2021).

Therefore, to enhance the willingness of the general public to get vaccinated, it is essential to identify the underlying reasons for vaccine avoidance or hesitation. By understanding the justifications and arguments put forth by individuals or communities reluctant to receive vaccines, it becomes possible to devise effective strategies to address their concerns. Significant progress can be made in increasing vaccination rates by considering the causes of vaccine avoidance or reluctance and comprehensively understanding the reasons behind this hesitancy (Al-Qerem and Jarab, 2021; Dhama *et al.*, 2021). These issues are also related to poor health literacy, confusion over protection levels, perceived risk, and fears. These factors can erode the crucial beliefs and trust in accepting COVID-19 vaccination (Griffith *et al.*, 2021; Dhama *et al.*, 2021).

Methods of Data Collection

Ukhrul District, situated in the northeastern part of Manipur State, encompasses an area that spans between approximately 24° 29' and 25° 42' latitude and 94° 30' and 94° 45' longitude. It shares borders with Myanmar to the east, Kamjong District to the south, Kangpokpi and Senapati Districts to the west, and Nagaland State to the north. Including Kamjong District, the total area of Ukhrul District is 4544 square kilometers. According to the 2011 Census, the district comprises 213 inhabited villages, with no uninhabited villages. The majority of the population belongs to the Tangkhul Naga tribe. The district has a total population of 183,998, consisting of 94,718 males and 89,280 females. The sex ratio stands at 943 females per one thousand males. The overall literacy rate in the district is 81.4%, with a literacy rate of 85.5% for males and 76.9% for females.

With the COVID-19 pandemic, which remains active in all parts of the country, a telephonic interview was adopted to collect qualitative data. The real benefit of telephone interviews is that they allow quicker and more affordable data collection from geographically dispersed groups where field interviews or postal surveys have limitations (Thomas and Purdon, 1994). Moreover, telephone interviews, as opposed to face-to-face meetings, result in a more fair allocation of power among interview participants. The interviewee has more influence over the conversation when using the phone. It not only encourages the interviewee to speak honestly and freely, but it also gives the interviewee more control, allowing them to lead the conversation to areas they believe are relevant (Volg, 2013; Farooq, 2015). However, concerns about the data's quality have also been expressed compared to face-to-face interviews (Thomas and Purdon, 1994). The interviewer cannot interpret body language during a telephone interview, which is a

crucial communication tool for ensuring that communications are accurately conveyed. Face-to-face interviews provide the researcher with visual access to the interviewee's surroundings, enabling them to gather essential contextual data (Farooq, 2015). However, the paper is not about a debate between telephone and face-to-face interview methods. This method was chosen for data collection after considering the available options on the given subject.

A total of one hundred individuals who had not received the COVID-19 vaccine were interviewed for this study. The sample consisted of 65 males and 45 females, all aged eighteen and above. The participants were selected using the snowball random sampling method, which initially identified a few individuals who met the criteria and then asked them to refer other non-vaccinated individuals from their respective villages in the Ukhrol district of Manipur.

Telephonic interviews were conducted with the selected participants in July, August, and September 2022. Each interview began with the same question posed to all respondents: "What are your reasons for not receiving the COVID-19 vaccine?" The conversations with each participant were recorded and subsequently transcribed into English for analysis. Follow-up interviews were also conducted with some respondents to obtain a fuller picture of their views on the subject.

Each response was collated and grouped under the initial question to organise and analyse the data. The aim was to identify common categories or themes that emerged from the participant's responses to vaccine hesitancy. These categories represented the recurring patterns or explanations provided by the respondents. By organizing and interpreting the texts within these categories, a comprehensive analysis was conducted to gain insights into the underlying reasons for vaccine non-acceptance among the participants.

The process involved carefully reviewing the transcripts, identifying similar patterns or themes across different responses, and analysing the content within each category. The collected data were interpreted to understand the various perspectives, concerns, and beliefs that influenced the participants' decision not to receive the COVID-19 vaccine.

By employing this systematic approach, the study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of the factors contributing to vaccine hesitancy among the selected individuals from different villages in the Ukhrol district. The data analysis allowed for a comprehensive exploration of the reasons behind their vaccine hesitancy. It provided valuable insights that could inform strategies to address and mitigate vaccine hesitancy within the studied population. Overall, through the snowball random sampling method, telephonic interviews, transcription, categorisation,

interpretation, and analysis, the study aimed to shed light on the reasons for vaccine non-acceptance among the individuals interviewed from the Ukhrul district of Manipur.

Reasons for Hesitancy

Vaccine hesitation refers to people's reluctance to accept a vaccine that has been proven safe, effective, and made available to people for protection against infectious diseases (McDonald, 2015; Danabal *et al.*, 2021). Vaccine scepticism and denial have existed in societies since Jenner's smallpox vaccination. Moreover, anti-vaccination organisations have historically coexisted alongside advancements in vaccine technology (Leask, 2020; Danabal *et al.*, 2021). Accordingly, Dube *et al.* (2018) suggested a 5-C model to understand vaccine hesitancy. This model explains that vaccine hesitancy is driven by five main determinants: confidence, complacency, convenience, risk calculation, and collective responsibility (Danabal *et al.*, 2021).

Although a lack of COVID-19 vaccine was an issue at the beginning of the vaccination effort, this is no longer the case. The problem now is there are few takers, particularly among the rural population of the Ukhrul district, for various reasons. Despite the relentless awareness campaigns by the Manipur government and its agencies, messages failed to resonate with the people. As a result, they continue to resist and adopt the 'wait and watch' approach. Five significant reasons that cropped up from the respondents' responses are possible side effects, co-morbidity, disbelief in efficacy, government-manufactured disease, complacency, and fake news.

Possible side effects: Vaccine confidence, which includes trust in the vaccine's effectiveness and safety; the delivery system, including the reliability and competence of health services and professionals; and the perceived motivations of policymakers making vaccine decisions (Dasgupta *et al.*, 2021), is deficient among these people. Many are concerned about possible side effects and the safety of the COVID-19 vaccine. They are worried about clinical trials of the vaccine having moved too fast, ignoring the possible side effects. Indigenously developed Covaxin, for instance, was believed to have been approved by the Indian government even before the completion of the standard Phase III clinical trial. One of the respondents said,

“My family and I have no intention of receiving the COVID vaccine. The manner and the speed of the vaccine production are highly suspicious because new vaccine productions from past precedents give us an idea that it normally takes a minimum of 2-3 years. This was not the case with the COVID-19 vaccine. It was completed within a year, so we suspect it carries potential side effects, which we are unwilling to risk.”

Since most vaccines are developed over a long period, it is natural to wonder how the COVID-19 vaccines were approved so quickly. Unfortunately, many people do not know that vaccines take years to develop because it takes years for researchers to find funding and get approvals. However, emergency funding was made available immediately when the pandemic started, speeding up the process. Also, the availability of new technology made it possible for the vaccine to be made quickly (MHA, 2022). So, COVID-19 was made quickly but was carefully tested to ensure its safety.

The COVID-19 vaccine's immediate adverse effects are never pleasant, and the fear of experiencing them has intimidated many people into receiving the shot (TOI, 2021). Common symptoms include headache, fatigue, muscle and joint pain, fever, etc. One of the respondents said,

“I have heard from my friends who have taken the COVID vaccine dose that it leaves them with muscle fatigue, fever, nausea, and joint pain, sometimes prolonged for a week. These symptoms scared many of us to take the vaccine.”

Another one said, "It really scared me because my neighbour's arm was in pain for a long time after receiving the second dose." Similarly, another one said, "My friend got a severe allergy and injection lump, which scared many of us to take the COVID-19 vaccine."

However, recent studies have shown that many of these side effects are anxiety-related rather than the vaccination itself (TOI, 2021). Nonetheless, there are some immediate side effects of the COVID-19 vaccine, but most symptoms only last a few days. These symptoms are, in fact, the result of our body's natural reactions to the vaccine. According to two separate studies conducted by Polack *et al.* (2020) and Hause *et al.* (2022), individuals who received COVID-19 vaccines for up to 6 months experienced common side effects that were mild and transient, typically resolving within a few days. Moreover, the risk of severe side effects was determined to be very low. Notably, both studies found no evidence supporting the existence of any long-term side effects resulting from the administration of COVID-19 vaccines. Additionally, the comparison between vaccinated individuals and those who had not received the vaccine did not reveal any significant difference in the occurrence of long-term side effects.

The reports of vaccination death cases in the district of Ukhrul and other parts of the state have significantly impacted people's perception of COVID-19 vaccines. These unfortunate incidents have led to a heightened sense of death anxiety among the population. When individuals hear about vaccinated individuals experiencing severe outcomes, such as death, it naturally triggers fear and uncertainty regarding the safety and efficacy of the vaccines.

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These reports have added to the existing doubts and hesitancy that some people may already have had about getting vaccinated. The fear of potential adverse effects, including fatal ones, can lead individuals to question whether the benefits of vaccination outweigh the risks. This uncertainty can be particularly challenging for public health authorities and healthcare professionals trying to encourage vaccination and curb the spread of COVID-19. One of the respondents said,

“I have heard of a few people who have died soon after taking the vaccine. Although not sure it was due to the COVID vaccine, I'm scared. I don't want to put my life at risk of dying. Therefore, instead of taking the vaccine, I'm taking extra care not to catch the disease.”

There is no denying that some people, unfortunately, died soon after the vaccination. However, studies revealed that this could be due to their underlying diseases and could be coincidental. According to studies in the U.S., there is not enough evidence that the COVID-19 vaccine contributed to those fatalities, and clinical information such as death certificates, autopsy, and medical records establish no causal link to the COVID-19 vaccines (Smith, 2021; Lamptey, 2021).

COVID-19 vaccine is also perceived to cause infertility and sterility in women and men. Some individuals are under the impression that the government of India is employing the COVID-19 vaccination, just like they did with the polio vaccine, as a tool to curb the expansion of the Indian population. Just as one of the respondents said,

“I heard a lot of gossip and rumours that the COVID-19 vaccine is capable of causing infertility and sterility in women and men. To tell you frankly, I have no idea how far these rumours are true, but who knows government could also be using this vaccine and others to control our country's population growth.”

In response to these rumours Dr Soumya Swaminathan, WHO Chief Scientist, said there is no scientific evidence or truth to the claim that vaccines interfere with fertility, whether in men or women because vaccines activate an immune response against that specific protein or antigen of that virus or bacteria. In this case, the COVID vaccine stimulates both an antibody response and a cell-mediated immune response against the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein. As a result, they cannot interfere with the functioning of either men's or women's reproductive organs. Similarly, many other studies revealed that COVID-19 vaccination does not decrease male or female fertility. What can impact one's fertility, though, is getting COVID-19 (WHO, 2021; Wesseling *et al.*, 2022).

Co-morbidity: It is a medical term to describe a condition of a person with multiple diseases existing simultaneously. People with more than one medical condition often have a heightened level of anxiety around COVID-19 and a unique perspective toward vaccination against the virus. Thus, some people at a perceived higher risk may be more concerned about vaccinating (Dhama *et al.*, 2021). Similarly, Umakanthan *et al.* (2021) suggested that the most common reasons for vaccine refusal were panic-stricken post-vaccination adverse effects, the existence of co-morbidity, and a lack of clarity in the provided vaccine information. People with one or more of these morbidities, cancer, chronic liver and kidney diseases, diabetes, and heart problems, constitute this category. For example, one respondent said, “Although I wish to receive the COVID-19 vaccine, I'm a patient with chronic liver disease. Thus, I'm not very confident about taking it.” Another respondent with cancer said,

“It truly scared me to take this vaccine because I have been told that two of the people who have died soon after taking the COVID-19 vaccine at Ukhrul district were cancer and diabetic patients.”

Similarly, another respondent suffering from heart disease said, “Many of my friends and family advised me not to take the vaccine. What if I take it, and it deteriorates my heart condition.”

The lack of information regarding the nature and protective benefits of COVID-19 vaccines has been a significant challenge among many individuals. Unfortunately, this has led to a lack of awareness about how vaccination can safeguard them from COVID-19. In truth, people of all age groups, particularly those with one or more pre-existing medical conditions, face a heightened risk of developing severe COVID-19, which could potentially lead to hospitalisation or even death (UNICEF, 2021). The limited understanding of the vaccines' mechanisms and protective effects has contributed to vaccine hesitancy and misinformation. This hesitancy is particularly concerning for individuals who are already vulnerable due to pre-existing health conditions. These medical conditions, such as diabetes, heart disease, respiratory disorders, and immunosuppression, can weaken the body's ability to combat infections, making them more susceptible to severe COVID-19 outcomes.

Disbelief in the efficacy of the vaccine: Disbelief in vaccine efficacy can promote vaccine reluctance. According to research, vaccination belief is determined by confidence in vaccine effectiveness, faith in healthcare practitioners, and trust in lawmakers who develop vaccination laws. Researchers observe a decline in public faith in vaccinations. People's psychological perspectives, such as how dangerous they think vaccinations are, how severe and dangerous they believe the disease is, how necessary they think the vaccine is, and how good they think they are at getting vaccinated, as well as how much they believe vaccinations cost and how good they

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think they are at getting them, affect vaccination complacency (MacDonald, 2015; Larson *et al.*, 2011; Dhama *et al.*, 2021). For example, Adivasi people were hesitant to get the COVID-19 vaccine because of rumours about how they were made, how well they worked, and how reliable they were. Some of India's tribal people think the COVID-19 vaccines are not good enough to stop this deadly disease. Some people believe that vaccines cause infertility and other problems, and others feel that vaccines make it easier to get COVID-19 (Iyer, 2021; Mehmooda *et al.*, 2021).

Similarly, several participants in this research believed that the COVID-19 vaccination does not protect against infection or reinfection with the virus. One of the respondents said,

“There is no absolute proof that this vaccine can protect me from infection. Many people still got reinfected by the virus even after taking the first and second doses of the vaccine. So what is the point of taking if I can still be infected.”

Another one said,

“I have heard that there are many cases of reinfections even after taking the complete doses of vaccine. So this whole vaccination campaign appears to be a placebo medication.”

Similarly, another one said, “It is not a serious disease. Whether I take the vaccine or not, if I would get infected, I will get.”

It is not surprising, particularly for the rural inhabitants, given the poor outreach, inaccessibility of their place, illiteracy, a poor network of information dissemination centres, age, employment status, poor interest in the COVID-19 vaccine, and disbelief in health care and government policies during the pandemic were all linked to rejection and delay in receiving the COVID-19 vaccine (Soares *et al.*, 2021; Dhama *et al.*, 2021). In addition, several other studies also reported that concerns regarding adverse events, unduly rapid vaccine development, and poor vaccine efficacy as some of the possible reasons for vaccine hesitancy among medical students (Manning *et al.*, 2021; Taylor *et al.*, 2020; Lucia *et al.*, 2021; Qiao *et al.*, 2022; Jain *et al.*, 2021). It again brings us to the level of awareness about the COVID-19 vaccine. It suggested that the knowledge about the vaccine, which does not give complete immunity to an individual but reduces the severity and prevents people from hospitalisation, is still lacking among these people.

A Government-manufactured disease: Similar to the myths that abound among the African American community that AIDS was created by the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) to exterminate African Americans and gays rather than being caused by a virus (Turner, 1993; Duesberg, 1996), some people also perceived COVID-19 disease as a creation of the Indian

government to control its citizens and the Manipur Government to avail more COVID-related funds. One of the respondents said,

“During the first wave of COVID-19, when there was a mass exodus of migrant workers back to their hometown, many test results were labelled as positive, while their close acquaintances whom they lived and travelled together either by flight, train or bus were not. How can this be, if not to increase the number of positive cases.”

Another respondent said,

“I heard many people who underwent testing with a slight fever or cough, or sinus problem came out positive in their test results; thus, keeping people away from undergoing the test. There was also a rumour that the state government received a huge sum of COVID-related funds from the central government. Therefore, the more the COVID infected cases, the more fund was sanctioned by the central government. Thus, the number of positive cases was rampantly increased to receive more funds without proper testing.”

Similarly, another respondent said, “I heard a rumour that COVID-19 is nothing but a government-manufactured disease to control or tame the people.”

Evidence of distrust towards the government is clearly visible in these people's responses, indicating the confusing state of their perceptions of COVID-19 as real or fiction which could be an offshoot of misunderstanding leading to mistrust. Misunderstanding distrust can compound distrust (Heller, 2015). Studies carried out by the WHO (2018), CDC (2015), and Pew Research Centre (2019) identified various factors linked to vaccine hesitancy. The research showed that individuals who had misconceptions about the risks and benefits of vaccines were more inclined to exhibit vaccine hesitancy. Additionally, there was a correlation between vaccine hesitancy and individuals who harbored a sense of distrust toward the government. Furthermore, the studies highlighted that those who had experienced negative incidents with vaccines in the past were more prone to expressing vaccine hesitancy.

It also shows facts about the origin and spread of COVID-19 being overwhelmed by false rumours. Talking of HIV/AIDS, Knight (2002) suggested that rumours do more than indicate distrust; they reinforce it by giving a clear explanation of who is to blame: a disease that can be traced to a deliberate (and familiar) actor instead of a social and health problem that is part of impersonal modernity and has complex causes that can make a person feel helpless and hopeless. Negative behaviours and a lack of information are the most detrimental factors that contribute to vaccine reluctance. Poor management of awareness-raising initiatives results in a considerable decline in public understanding of vaccination and its related modes of action (Arede, 2019).

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Complacency and Convenience: Vaccine hesitation, according to Noronha *et al.* (2021), ranges from the vaccine's side effects (confidence) and the belief that others need the vaccination more than the individual (complacency). It develops when the individual's perceived risks of the disease are minimal, and vaccination is not considered an essential preventative measure (Dasgupta *et al.*, 2021). Vaccination convenience includes physical availability, affordability, and willingness to pay (for those who aren't eligible for or don't want to use the government programme), as well as the ability to understand (language and health literacy) and appeal of the vaccine and the real or perceived quality of service (MacDonald, 2015). For example, one of the respondents said,

“I have not taken the vaccine because I don't expect to get a COVID-19 infection. Even if I get it, it is not a serious disease like any common cold or fever. So there is no need for vaccination. I think I'll be fine.”

Another respondent said,

“Some of my neighbours have been infected, but I feel I will not get the virus. As others said, the government is exaggerating the disease for whatever reason; I have no idea.”

On a different note, one of the respondents said,

“Although the vaccine is provided free of cost, it is not always available in the villages as in cities and towns. So far, the campaign to vaccinate people has occurred twice, particularly in rural areas, one during the first round of doses and the other during the second. It is also partly because our village's primary health centre has no doctor or nurse. Moreover, ASHA workers are also poorly skilled and equipped. As a result, so many of us have missed taking the vaccine. Moreover, it is also not possible for many of us to go to the district town just to get the vaccine. And so we remain unvaccinated.”

Not only reluctance to the COVID-19 vaccine but vaccine convenience – availability, and accessibility are important reasons many rural inhabitants remain unvaccinated. As Tolia *et al.* (2022) suggested regarding vaccine adoption in Gujarat, many government-run health centres in rural areas remain non-operational, making it difficult for the inhabitants to get the vaccine. The same is true for the rural inhabitants of the Ukhrlul district. Though primary health centres are available in the government record, they all suffer from 'missing doctors and nurses syndromes' except for a few. Therefore, accessibility and availability of vaccines constitute one of the most significant barriers to any vaccination campaign in India. Moreover, it is vital to identify vaccine hesitancy and unvaccinated people due to accessibility and availability to achieve a greater vaccination height.

Fake news: The COVID-19 vaccination campaign faces significant challenges due to the persistent presence of rumours, fake news, misinformation, and limited information. Despite efforts to debunk and dispel false narratives and conspiracy theories from various sources like Whatsapp and the internet, these misleading pieces of information continue to hinder vaccination efforts, contributing to vaccine hesitancy among certain groups of people. The circulation of fake news and false rumours has created an atmosphere of uncertainty and doubt surrounding COVID-19 vaccines. This misinformation often spreads rapidly through social media platforms and other online channels, reaching a wide audience. As a result, individuals who are exposed to such misleading content may become hesitant or skeptical about the safety and efficacy of vaccines. Conspiracy theories, thought to have been debunked, still linger in the minds of a large number of people, leading to unfounded fears and apprehensions about getting vaccinated. This perpetuates a cycle of vaccine hesitancy, preventing these individuals from taking the necessary steps to protect themselves and their communities.

Limitations of the Study

The study has several limitations. A relatively small sample size may not potentially represent the entire unvaccinated populations in the study area. Data were collected thorough telephonic interview, which might have limited the nuances of the study. The study overlooks the cultural beliefs and practices and their historical context as well as the association of socioeconomic factors, age, and gender, which might impact vaccination decisions.

Discussion and Conclusion

The COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy continues to exist at large across a wide range of people for various reasons as indicated in the findings, and the abysmal figure for vaccinated people remains a testament for the study area. Complacency, rumours, conspiracy theories, misinformation, fake news surrounding the vaccine, inaccessibility and availability, time dimension as is prevalent in rural areas, distrust toward government and health care workers, and belief in the anti-vaccine propaganda which were thought to have been debunked, continue to fuel the persistence of vaccine hesitancy in the region that may come as a stumbling block against any possible vaccine drive in future. The efforts of the government and its agencies to discredit inaccurate information about the vaccine have been largely defeated. People are less informed about the correct details of the vaccine to counter false information, particularly in rural areas. As a result, the COVID-19 vaccination campaign has also either amplified pre-existing scepticism or introduced whole new ones. Insufficient knowledge of vaccination safety

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and effectiveness, a lack of access to the vaccine, a lack of transparency around the vaccine approval process in India, and the spread of false information are among the new factors. The government's incapacity to address civil-rights issues concerning vaccination drives and its overall COVID-19 management plan is reflected in the emergence of anti-vaccine subcultures, which is indicative of the failure of the government's vaccine communication strategy. Issues like the vaccine's potential adverse consequences on women's health, fertility, and functionality are not adequately addressed (Tarfe, 2021).

Applying medical anthropology: Robert Hahn, an eminent medical anthropologist and epidemiologist said theories that fail to account for the constant interaction of different levels of society are problematic. Disease is not only biological but also social, which is why social science should focus on disease control and prevention (Hahn, 2020). Similarly, a medical anthropologist, Sabina Rashid, said, "When you have a very biomedical response, you miss cultural opportunities to do adequate risk communication. Context matters" (Svoboda, 2021).

Since the COVID-19 pandemic is a social phenomenon, the response must also be social. Vaccine hesitancy is not a new phenomenon in the long history of vaccination campaigns. So what can medical anthropology offer to mitigate this problem? An individual's decision to receive a vaccine entails the composition of personal, cultural, social, spiritual, political, and economic factors (Umakanthan *et al.*, 2021). According to Piltch-Loeb and DiClemente (2021), the vaccine uptake continuum consists of five factors: (1) knowledge of the health danger; (2) vaccine availability; (3) vaccine accessibility; (4) vaccine affordability; and (5) vaccine acceptance. We may better understand the variables influencing vaccination hesitancy by addressing each continuum stage methodically. More significantly, we can begin conceptualising, creating, executing, and evaluating effective interventions to encourage vaccine uptake. Out of all the existing theories in medical anthropology, the most promising in addressing the continuum of these factors is the 'anthropology of medicine.' Anthropological medicine is a theory and approach that focuses on understanding sickness and health from a cultural and social perspective. It considers how people view and experience illness, including the ideas and attitudes of both healthcare professionals and the general public. It recognises that sickness can have social and cultural causes, not just physical or environmental ones. It also values the influence of society and culture on healing and therapy processes. This approach emphasises the well-being of both patients and healers and integrates cultural understanding with medical education, practice, and research (Hahn, 1995). Likewise, it offers some meaningful solutions to mitigate vaccine hesitancy.

First is the importance of listening (Hahn, 1995). Patient listening and understanding of people's doubts and queries surrounding the COVID-19 vaccine and then providing them with facts, figures, and data to clarify their issues could enhance mutual understanding and the likelihood of even convincing the people to receive the vaccine. Past studies have shown that listening has led to successful health programs like the Polela Health Center in South Africa (Hahn, 1995; Rooke, n.d.). For instance, when international health organisations first constructed treatment facilities for Ebola patients in 2014, these facilities had opaque walls that made it impossible for the patient's families to see what was happening to their loved ones. In addition, messages about the disease were conveyed in a language locals could not understand. But later, compliance with doctors grew as the messaging became more sensitive, and the walls of treatment facilities were redone to be transparent. Thus, it is vital to pay attention to local voices (Tett, 2021).

Second, anthropological medicine recognises the significance of knowing people's social environments, economic status, access to resources, and exposure to multiple sources of information. It is concerned with gaining an insider's perspective, understanding reality, and beliefs and attitudes to provide a practical solution to people's problems. As a result, medical anthropologists often develop comprehensive, highly contextualised accounts of health issues in terms of a wide range of interconnected factors because they tend to take a holistic, contextual approach, viewing attitudes and behaviours within the natural social settings they emerge and function (Singer and Baer, 2007). For example, health workers can employ an ethnographic approach – often go to the village, listen to people's doubts and confusion, and devise a better effective plan to reduce hesitancy. Otherwise, a barrier like the unavailability of the vaccine could be misjudged as reluctance. There is a tendency to club unvaccinated people under the umbrella of hesitancy or unwillingness. However, there could be various factors for not receiving the vaccine, unavailability and inaccessibility being important factors in this study.

Thirdly, anthropology of medicine can help address the need for explaining, translating, and brokering in health care systems (Hahn, 1995). For example, people may not understand vaccine development processes, preventive behaviour like COVID Standard Operating Procedure (SOP), side effects, and other related issues. Therefore, the need for social marketing intervention at the village level with the use of community leaders, village institutions like churches, village councils, equipping medical staff and facilities of their health centres could significantly increase their trust and intention to vaccinate (Kashyap, 2021; Tolia *et al.*, 2022).

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Robert Hahn (2020), an expert member of the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), USA, said,

“Each time there is an outbreak – not just in the United States – It is clear that people affected by the outbreaks don't do what they're 'supposed' to do. People continue to have unsafe sex. They go to funerals and wash the bodies of their loved ones. They resist wearing masks. Even when deadly pathogens are at stake, customs, religions, and other social factors often win out. A few months into an outbreak, the CDC will typically say: 'Why are people continuing to do these things that are spreading the disease? Maybe we could use some anthropologists.' They use them, but it is always late in the game. It's never a routine part of planning a response to public health problems. I can only speculate about the roots of this resistance – it could be a persistent belief that sickness is basically a biological phenomenon, a lack of awareness of the anthropological roots of public health, or suspicion of a discipline that does not appear as scientific as biology or epidemiology” (Hahn, 2020: 2).

Furthermore, Foster and Anderson (1978) introduced 'preventive medicine and the maintenance concept' to understand the difficulties of traditional people in changing their health behaviour. According to them, traditional peoples' etiological ideas and therapeutic interview images share one important premise. That is, illness or disease is manifested through pain and suffering. People find it hard to accept that a major illness might grow slowly and be discovered when it is too late to help. As long as their body functions normally, they are healthy, and the need to develop preventive measures before disease occurrence is far from their medical logic. Thus they said traditional peoples are not good candidates for preventive medicine, which focuses on preventing sickness through vaccination or early detection. Preventive medications are incompatible with traditional people's worldview, and they will not accept them with the same zeal as Europeans and Americans.

The same principle can also be applied to understanding COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy. If the concept of prevention does not exist in people's healthcare system, the COVID-19 vaccination campaign will face resistance. At this juncture, the anthropology of medicine equipped with cultural competency can greatly help convince people of the significance of vaccination. Moreover, it helps to realise that everybody does not necessarily perceive the vaccine's benefits the same way others might (Foster and Anderson, 1978). So, cultural knowledge and understanding other cultures make it easier for providers, patients, and institutions to work together. This perspective gives healthcare professionals an account of how patients, families, and friends conceptualise health problems and will respond to proposed care. Cultural competency and sensitivity improve clinical practice and community health efficacy by

enabling changes in professional style, institutional practises, and community behaviours where appropriate. Understanding a patient's personal and social life in connection to the treatment plan aids in successful communication, resource utilisation, and treatment effectiveness (Winkalman, 2008). Thus, the social and cultural forms of the recipients must be understood to design better health programs (Foster and Anderson, 1978).

Gillian Tett, a trained cultural anthropologist, said even in the United States and some other rich countries, the COVID-19 vaccine distribution has proven to be miserable and inequitable, not because of the structures of the global political economy but culture. According to her, effective responses to fast-moving (or even slow-moving) challenges necessitate more than dependence on so-called hard sciences, such as medical research or big data powers. Understanding human behaviour and society requires 'soft' science as well. It requires a lateral approach to cope not just with pandemics but also with a slew of other global issues. Because anthropologists prefer to adopt a worm's-eye view (that is, look at things from the bottom up, holistically), studying other cultures provides a distinct perspective from the bird's-eye (top-down) assessments. Government must not ignore the cultural and environmental context of people's lives since people rarely think about risk the way scientists do. For example, when vaccination messages were initially delivered to the public only through the voices of the 'elites' (doctors, scientists, etc.) in the U.S. and Europe, they failed to resonate with all sections of people; later, they switched to community voices and it produced results. Thus in any intervention effort or policy implementation, top-down models are insufficient. One also needs a worm's-eye view, considering people's social and cultural factors (Tett, 2021). This could be one lesson we have learnt from COVID-19 infection.

Acknowledgement

I sincerely extend my heartfelt gratitude to my friends, Mr Pamreingam Lungleng and Mr Mayopam Khareng, for assisting in my data collection and identifying my study participants.

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Manuscript received on: October 10, 2022

Manuscript accepted on: August 24, 2023